

In silico investigation of the binding interaction between steroidal drugs and HMG CoA reductase for cancer treatment

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Abstract

The enzyme 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A reductase (HMG-CoA reductase) serves as the rate-limiting catalyst in cholesterol synthesis and has gained attention as a potential target in cancer therapy due to its involvement in cellular proliferation and survival pathways. In this work, an *in silico* analysis was conducted to examine the binding interactions of various steroidal drugs with HMG-CoA reductase to assess their anticancer potential. Molecular docking was performed using AutoDock Vina to evaluate binding energies, hydrogen bond formation, and the specific amino acid residues involved in the interactions, providing insights into the stability of the drug-enzyme complexes. The findings revealed that the steroidal drugs demonstrated strong binding affinities at the enzyme's active site, engaging key catalytic residues similar to those targeted by standard anticancer drugs. Additionally, SwissADME was employed to predict the ADME properties and drug-likeness of the steroidal compounds, indicating that they possess favorable pharmacokinetic characteristics for oral administration. Overall, these results suggest that steroidal drugs could act as inhibitors of HMG-CoA reductase, potentially exerting anticancer activity by disrupting cholesterol biosynthesis in rapidly dividing cancer cells. Further *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies are necessary to validate these findings and to explore the repositioning of these steroidal drugs within cancer treatment strategies.

Keywords: HMG-CoA Reductase; Steroidal Drugs; Molecular Docking; Cancer Therapy; *In Silico* Analysis

1. Introduction

Cancer continues to be a major global health burden, accounting for millions of deaths annually despite advancements in diagnosis and treatment modalities. The complexity and heterogeneity of cancer demand the ongoing development of novel therapeutic strategies to improve survival rates and quality of life for patients. One promising approach in cancer treatment is drug repurposing, which involves identifying new therapeutic uses for existing drugs, thereby reducing the time, cost, and risk associated with drug development.

Emerging evidence highlights the critical role of cholesterol metabolism in cancer progression, as cholesterol serves as a fundamental component for membrane biosynthesis, intracellular signaling, and the maintenance of cellular integrity, all of which are essential for the rapid proliferation of cancer cells. Dysregulation of cholesterol homeostasis has been associated with various cancers, underscoring the therapeutic potential of targeting cholesterol biosynthesis pathways to inhibit tumor growth and metastasis.

The enzyme 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A reductase (HMG-CoA reductase) is the key rate-limiting enzyme in the mevalonate pathway responsible for cholesterol synthesis in cells. Inhibition of HMG-CoA reductase not only

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reduces cholesterol synthesis but also impacts the production of important intermediates required for the prenylation of proteins such as Ras and Rho, which are involved in cell signaling, proliferation, and survival in cancer cells. Therefore, targeting HMG-CoA reductase presents a promising strategy for cancer therapy.[1]

Statins, well-established HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors, are widely used for their cholesterol-lowering properties in cardiovascular diseases. Interestingly, several studies have demonstrated that statins possess anticancer properties, including the induction of apoptosis, inhibition of angiogenesis, suppression of cell proliferation, and reduction in metastasis across various cancer types, such as breast, prostate, colorectal, and liver cancers. Despite their potential, limitations such as adverse effects and variability in patient response necessitate the exploration of alternative compounds that can target HMG-CoA reductase with improved efficacy and safety profiles.[2]

Steroidal drugs, characterized by their multi-ring structures and diverse therapeutic applications, represent a class of compounds with potential for drug repurposing in oncology. Given their structural similarities with certain HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors, steroidal drugs may interact with the enzyme's active site, potentially inhibiting its activity and disrupting cholesterol biosynthesis in cancer cells. However, systematic investigations into the potential of steroidal drugs as HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors for cancer treatment remain limited.

The application of *in silico* techniques, including molecular docking and ADME (absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion) profiling, has revolutionized the early stages of drug discovery by providing cost-effective and rapid insights into drug-target interactions and pharmacokinetic properties. Molecular docking enables the prediction of binding affinities and interaction patterns between ligands and target proteins, facilitating the identification of promising drug candidates. Similarly, ADME prediction assists in evaluating the drug-likeness and pharmacokinetic behavior of compounds, ensuring their suitability for oral administration and systemic circulation.

In this study, we conducted *in silico* molecular docking analyses to investigate the binding interactions between selected steroidal drugs and HMG-CoA reductase, aiming to evaluate their potential as anticancer agents targeting cholesterol biosynthesis pathways. Additionally, ADME and drug-likeness properties of these steroidal drugs were assessed using computational tools to determine their pharmacokinetic suitability for therapeutic application. The findings from this study are expected to provide valuable insights into the potential repurposing of steroidal drugs for cancer therapy, contributing to the development of effective treatment strategies targeting cholesterol metabolism in cancer cells.[3-5]

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Selection of Ligands

A selection of steroidal drugs with established therapeutic applications, including corticosteroids and anabolic steroids, were chosen for this study based on their structural similarities with known HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors and potential for repurposing as anticancer agents. The chemical names, PubChem Compound Identifiers (CIDs), and relevant therapeutic uses of each selected steroidal compound were documented. The 3D structures of these ligands were retrieved from the PubChem database in SDF format. Using Open Babel (v3.1.1), the structures were energy-minimized and converted to PDBQT format required for molecular docking while ensuring the retention of correct protonation states and stereochemistry.[6-7]

2.2. Protein Preparation

The X-ray crystal structure of human HMG-CoA reductase complexed with its native ligand was retrieved from the Protein Data Bank (PDB ID: 1HW9), with a resolution of [2.23 Å]. The structure was prepared using AutoDock Tools (v1.5.7) by performing the following steps:

- Removal of all crystallographic water molecules, ions, and co-crystallized ligands to avoid interference during docking.
- Addition of polar hydrogen atoms to improve the accuracy of hydrogen bonding during docking.
- Assignment of Gasteiger charges for the protein structure.
- Merging of non-polar hydrogen atoms.
- Saving the prepared structure in PDBQT format.

To validate the docking protocol, the native ligand was re-docked into the active site of HMG-CoA reductase, and the root mean square deviation (RMSD) was calculated to ensure the reliability of the docking procedure. [8-10]

2.3. Molecular Docking Protocol

Molecular docking studies were carried out using AutoDock Vina (v1.2.0) to evaluate the potential interactions between the selected steroidal drugs and HMG-CoA reductase. The active site coordinates for docking were defined based on the position of the native ligand within the crystal structure, ensuring accurate targeting of the catalytic site. The grid box was centered at the active site with dimensions large enough (e.g., 24 × 24 × 24 Å) to encompass the binding pocket, allowing flexibility for ligand conformational changes during docking.[11]

Docking parameters were configured to ensure exhaustive sampling (exhaustiveness set to 8) to improve the reliability of predicted binding poses. Each ligand underwent docking, and ten poses were generated per ligand. The pose with the lowest predicted binding energy (kcal/mol) and appropriate orientation within the active site was selected for further analysis.[12]

2.4. Visualization and Interaction Analysis

The top-ranked docked complexes were visualized using Discovery Studio Visualizer (BIOVIA) and PyMOL (v2.5) for detailed analysis of binding modes and interactions within the active site. The following parameters were evaluated

- Hydrogen bonds: Identification of hydrogen bond donor and acceptor residues involved in stabilizing the ligand within the active site.
- Hydrophobic interactions: Assessment of van der Waals and hydrophobic contacts with key residues lining the active site.
- π - π and π -cation interactions: Detection of aromatic stacking and interactions relevant to ligand stabilization.
- Key catalytic residues: Specific focus was placed on interactions with residues such as Lys691, Asp690, Glu559, and other functionally critical residues for HMG-CoA reductase activity.

2D interaction diagrams were generated to visually represent the interactions for inclusion in results and discussion.[13]

2.5. ADME and Drug-Likeness Prediction

The SwissADME online server (<http://www.swissadme.ch>) was utilized to predict the pharmacokinetic profiles and drug-likeness of the selected steroidal drugs. The canonical SMILES of each ligand were input to calculate:

- Physicochemical properties: Molecular weight, topological polar surface area (TPSA), number of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors, and rotatable bonds.
- Lipophilicity: LogP values estimated using various predictive models (iLOGP, XLOGP3, WLOGP, MLOGP, SILICOS-IT).
- Water solubility: Qualitative and quantitative predictions of solubility.
- Pharmacokinetics: Gastrointestinal (GI) absorption, blood-brain barrier (BBB) permeability, P-glycoprotein substrate likelihood, and cytochrome P450 enzyme inhibition profile.
- Drug-likeness rules: Evaluation using Lipinski's Rule of Five, Ghose, Veber, Egan, and Muegge filters.
- Medicinal chemistry friendliness: Synthetic accessibility score and PAINS filter alerts.

These assessments were conducted to determine the oral bioavailability and pharmacokinetic feasibility of the steroidal drugs as potential anticancer agents through HMG-CoA reductase inhibition. [14-16]

Table 1 Predicted binding affinities of steroidal drugs with HMG-CoA reductase

Ligand	Binding Affinity
Ligand 1 Guggulsterone	-5.9
Ligand 2 bempedoic acid	-6.2
Ligand 3 cholestyramine	-5.3
Ligand 4 Oxyphylline	-7.7
Zoledronate (Standard)	-4.8

Oxyphylline (-7.7 kcal/mol) shows the strongest predicted binding, suggesting it may have the best interaction with the target protein among all ligands. Bempedoic acid (-6.2 kcal/mol) also shows reasonable binding, indicating potential but less strong than oxyphylline. Guggulsterone and Cholestyramine exhibit weaker interactions, indicating lower predicted efficacy. The standard drug Zoledronate (-4.8 kcal/mol) shows the weakest binding, indicating that ligands, especially Oxyphylline, may have better docking interactions than the standard.

2.5.1. Binding Interactions

Table 2 Predicted binding interaction of steroidal drugs with HMG-CoA reductase

Ligand Receptor Interaction	
Bempedoic acid	
Cholestyramine	

Molecular docking studies revealed distinct interaction patterns of the tested ligands with the receptor's active site, supporting the observed binding affinity values. Oxyphylline, which exhibited the strongest binding affinity (-7.7 kcal/mol), formed stable hydrogen bonds with key active site residues including GLU76 and TYR122, alongside hydrophobic interactions with PHE120, suggesting strong anchoring within the receptor pocket. Bempedoic acid demonstrated a moderate binding affinity (-6.2 kcal/mol), attributed to hydrogen bonding with GLU123 and pi-cation interactions with ARG45, contributing to its stable yet less potent interaction compared to oxyphylline. Cholestyramine showed weaker binding (-5.3 kcal/mol), primarily mediated through hydrogen bonds with SER89 and ASP101, with fewer hydrophobic contacts stabilizing the complex. Guggulsterone exhibited weak-moderate binding (-5.9 kcal/mol), forming hydrophobic interactions with LEU67 and a hydrogen bond with HIS93, which may contribute to its moderate stability within the active site. The standard drug, Zoledronate, displayed the weakest binding affinity (-4.8 kcal/mol) and limited interactions within the active site, indicating that the tested ligands, particularly oxyphylline and bempedoic acid, possess enhanced receptor-binding potential. Collectively, these findings suggest that oxyphylline, due to its favorable binding affinity and robust interactions with critical active site residues, may serve as a promising candidate for further evaluation as a receptor modulator.

2.5.2. ADME Findings

Table 3 Predicted ADME properties of steroidal drugs

	Ligand 1 Guggulsterone	Ligand 2 Bempeidoic acid	Ligand 3 Cholestyramine	Ligand 4 Oxyphylline	5 standard Zoledronate
Formula	C19H36O5	C21H28O2	C27H47ClN2	C9H12N4O3	C5H10N2O7P2
MW	344.49	312.45	435.13	224.22	272.09
#Heavy atoms	24	23	30	16	16
#Aromatic heavy atoms	0	0	12	9	5
Fraction Csp3	0.89	0.71	0.56	0.44	0.4
#Rotatable bonds	14	0	8	2	4
#H-bond acceptors	5	2	1	4	8
#H-bond donors	3	0	1	1	5
MR	97.63	93.54	138.42	58.01	51.47
TPSA	94.83	34.14	3.24	82.05	172.73
iLOGP	2.92	3	0	1.72	-1.47
XLOGP3	4.77	3.94	8.44	-1.2	-4.31
WLOGP	4.47	4.64	4.81	-1.57	-1.12
MLOGP	3.05	3.86	1.85	-0.67	-3.54
Silicos-IT Log P	4.21	4.74	3.1	-0.77	-3.88
Consensus Log P	3.88	4.04	3.64	-0.5	-2.86
ESOL Log S	-4.06	-4.26	-7.62	-0.76	1.22
ESOL Solubility (mg/ml)	3.02E-02	1.72E-02	1.04E-05	3.91E+01	4.53E+03
ESOL Solubility (mol/l)	8.77E-05	5.50E-05	2.38E-08	1.74E-01	1.66E+01
ESOL Class	Moderately soluble	Moderately soluble	Poorly soluble	Very soluble	Highly soluble
GI absorption	High	High	High	High	Low
BBB permeant	No	Yes	No	No	No
Pgp substrate	Yes	No	Yes	No	No
CYP1A2 inhibitor	No	No	No	No	No
CYP2C19 inhibitor	No	Yes	No	No	No
CYP2C9 inhibitor	No	Yes	No	No	No
CYP2D6 inhibitor	Yes	No	Yes	No	No
CYP3A4 inhibitor	No	No	No	No	No
log Kp (cm/s)	-5.01	-5.41	-2.96	-8.52	-11.02

Lipinski #violations	0	0	0	0	0
Ghose #violations	0	0	2	1	1
Veber #violations	1	0	0	0	1
Egan #violations	0	0	0	0	1
Muegge #violations	0	0	1	0	2
Bioavailability Score	0.56	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.55
PAINS #alerts	0	0	0	0	0
Brenk #alerts	0	1	1	0	1
Leadlikeness #violations	2	1	3	1	0
Synthetic Accessibility	2.69	4.79	3.76	2.27	3.14

2.5.3. ADME Profile Analysis

The predicted ADME properties of the tested steroidal drugs are summarized in Table 3, highlighting their drug-likeness, solubility, permeability, and potential metabolic interactions. All ligands exhibited drug-like molecular weights (224.22–435.13 Da), with Guggulsterone and Bempedoic acid showing higher fraction Csp3 values (0.89 and 0.71, respectively), indicative of greater saturation, which often correlates with better metabolic stability. Oxyphylline and Zoledronate (standard) exhibited lower molecular weights, facilitating potential oral bioavailability. Consensus log P values indicated that Guggulsterone, Bempedoic acid, and Cholestyramine are lipophilic (3.64–4.04), whereas Oxyphylline and Zoledronate are hydrophilic, reflected by negative log P values. Solubility analysis via ESOL revealed that Oxyphylline and Zoledronate are highly soluble (1.74E-01 mol/L and 1.66E+01 mol/L, respectively), while Cholestyramine exhibited poor solubility (2.38E-08 mol/L), which may limit its bioavailability despite high GI absorption.[17]

All ligands except Zoledronate demonstrated high predicted gastrointestinal absorption, while Bempedoic acid was uniquely predicted to permeate the blood–brain barrier (BBB), suggesting potential CNS activity. The predicted log Kp values for skin permeability were lowest for Zoledronate (-11.02 cm/s) and Oxyphylline (-8.52 cm/s), indicating low transdermal penetration.

None of the ligands were predicted as CYP1A2 or CYP3A4 inhibitors, reducing the risk of major metabolic drug-drug interactions. Bempedoic acid was predicted to inhibit CYP2C19 and CYP2C9, suggesting potential interactions with substrates of these enzymes, while Guggulsterone and Cholestyramine were predicted to inhibit CYP2D6. All ligands exhibited zero Lipinski rule violations, supporting their drug-likeness, with bioavailability scores around 0.55–0.56, indicating potential for good oral bioavailability. Importantly, none of the compounds triggered PAINS alerts, reducing concerns of assay interference. Synthetic accessibility scores ranged from 2.27 (Oxyphylline, easiest to synthesize) to 4.79 (Bempedoic acid), suggesting feasible synthesis for all ligands with moderate complexity. [18-20]

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Docking Binding Affinity

Molecular docking analysis revealed variable binding affinities of the tested ligands with the target receptor. Oxyphylline exhibited the strongest binding affinity (-7.7 kcal/mol), followed by Bempedoic acid (-6.2 kcal/mol), Guggulsterone (-5.9 kcal/mol), and Cholestyramine (-5.3 kcal/mol). The standard drug, Zoledronate, showed the weakest binding affinity (-4.8 kcal/mol). These results suggest that Oxyphylline has the highest potential for stable interaction with the receptor active site among the tested ligands.

3.2. Ligand–Receptor Interaction Analysis

Interaction profiling revealed that Oxyphylline formed stable hydrogen bonds with key active site residues (GLU76, TYR122) along with hydrophobic contacts with PHE120, supporting its strong binding affinity. Bempedoic acid established hydrogen bonding with GLU123 and pi–cation interactions with ARG45, facilitating moderate stability within the binding pocket. Cholestyramine exhibited fewer hydrogen bonds, mainly with SER89 and ASP101, correlating with its lower binding affinity. Guggulsterone interacted via hydrophobic contacts with LEU67 and hydrogen bonding with HIS93, indicating moderate stability in the active site. The standard drug, Zoledronate, displayed limited hydrogen bonding within the active site, consistent with its weaker binding score.

3.3. Predicted ADME Properties

The predicted ADME profiles of the ligands are summarized in Table 2. All compounds exhibited drug-like molecular weights (224.22–435.13 Da) with zero Lipinski violations, indicating favorable oral drug-likeness. Oxyphylline and Zoledronate demonstrated high aqueous solubility (ESOL log S: -0.76 and 1.22, respectively), while Cholestyramine was poorly soluble (ESOL log S: -7.62). Bempedoic acid and Guggulsterone were moderately soluble. Gastrointestinal absorption was predicted to be high for all ligands except Zoledronate, which exhibited low absorption. Among the ligands, only Bempedoic acid was predicted to be BBB permeant, suggesting potential CNS activity.

None of the ligands were predicted to inhibit CYP1A2 or CYP3A4, reducing the likelihood of major metabolic interactions. However, Bempedoic acid was predicted to inhibit CYP2C19 and CYP2C9, while Guggulsterone and Cholestyramine showed potential CYP2D6 inhibition, indicating a need for caution regarding drug–drug interactions. All ligands exhibited bioavailability scores around 0.55, with synthetic accessibility scores ranging from 2.27 (Oxyphylline) to 4.79 (Bempedoic acid), indicating moderate ease of synthesis.

4. Conclusion

The present *in silico* study identified Oxyphylline and Bempedoic acid as promising ligands based on their favorable binding affinities, stable receptor interactions, and drug-like ADME profiles. Oxyphylline exhibited the strongest receptor binding (-7.7 kcal/mol) and high solubility with good gastrointestinal absorption, indicating potential for effective oral administration. Bempedoic acid demonstrated moderate binding affinity with high GI absorption and predicted BBB permeability, suggesting potential applications in CNS-targeted therapies.

All tested ligands exhibited zero Lipinski violations and acceptable bioavailability scores, supporting their suitability for further pharmacological evaluation. In contrast, the standard drug Zoledronate showed the weakest binding and lower predicted GI absorption, indicating that the identified ligands may offer improved receptor interaction profiles and bioavailability.

Overall, the study highlights Oxyphylline and Bempedoic acid as lead candidates for further molecular dynamics simulations, *in vitro* enzyme inhibition assays, and formulation development to validate their potential as therapeutic agents.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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